

Exploring the Relationship Between Multiple Sclerosis and HIV Infection, incorporating environmental factors in order to understand MS etiology: Insights from a Case Study

Author: Shaden Moutasem Naser Mahmoud

(BSC, Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Hashemite university)

Abstract:

This research investigates a case study of a patient that developed Relapsing-Remitting Multiple Sclerosis (RRMS) and then was Subsequently diagnosed with Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV). The RRMS symptoms disappeared after the diagnosis and initiating of HIV treatment. The absence of RRMS relapses and reaching no evidence of disease activity (NEDA) status provoke questions regarding the underlying mechanisms that link HIV infection to the remission of RRMS symptoms.

This study aims to comprehend the immunological interaction between HIV and RRMS that led to RRMS remission. Additionally, the study incorporates biological and environmental factors that explains RRMS etiology. The case study investigation alongside with various factors provide evidence to support a hypothesis proposing that DNA mutations can progress or remit RRMS depending on the modification done on the DNA. The HIV in this case led to upregulation and suppression in specific genes responsible for recognizing self-antigens and producing cytokines in T cells, therefore, these changes led to a reduced T cells attack on myelin sheaths. In different cases where patients were diagnosed with RRMS without HIV, biological factors such as viruses that integrate its own DNA in host genome dose alter genes which contribute to RRMS development and progression. Moreover, environmental factors such as Vitamin D level and radiation exposure amount can modify the genomic material in the host which increases the risk of RRMS incidence in those individuals. Finally, treatment options and its success rate in treating RRMS that is offered by clinical trials dose support the hypothesis.

Abbreviation:

MS Multiple sclerosis, NEDA No evidence of disease activity, EFS Event free survival, HAART Highly active antiretroviral therapy, HIV Human immunodeficiency virus, RRMS Relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis, MRI cranial magnetic resonance imaging, HSCT hematopoietic stem cell transplantation, HALT-MS High-dose immunosuppressive therapy and autologous hematopoietic cell transplantation for relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis.

Introduction:

Although the HAART and antiretroviral treatments helped in reducing MS symptoms in patients However in this case the patient experienced notable relief of MS symptoms after being diagnosed with HIV, the patient didn't experience any relapses when he was infected with the virus and before starting the treatment and continued to achieve NEDA statuses.

Case report:

Labella et al. (2021) presented a case were a male aged 23 who has previously been diagnosed with plaque psoriasis and then experienced a period of blurred vision lasting in his right eye for one week during April 2003, this was followed by difficulties with coordination, double vision (diplopia), and numbness on one side of his face approximately for one month later. A diagnosis of relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis RRMS was made based on the results obtained from an MRI scan which revealed lesions in the brain. Two further episodes occurred within the subsequent two years but resolved without intervention.

In July of 2006, the patient exhibited symptoms such as a widespread rash (exanthema), which later led to the diagnosis of syphilis and HIV infection. Treatment was administered specifically for syphilis, but HIV treatment wasn't administrated until 2009. Highly active antiretroviral therapy was initiated due to a decline in CD4+ lymphocyte levels. Since then, the patient's CD4+ lymphocyte count has remained steady at normal levels while also maintaining undetectable viral load associated with HIV infection.

From 2009 to 2020, his CD4+ lymphocyte counts consistently hovered around 700 cells/mm³.

The patient returned for regular check-ups in the Neurology Department starting from 2014 and displayed no symptoms or relapses or increased disability during

those visits. Sequential annual MRI scans revealed several new lesions near the ventricles compared to earlier scans; however, there was no visible contrast enhancement observed. Subsequent follow-ups were conducted until February of 2020. revealed no new lesions or clinical changes, and the patient achieved No Evidence of Disease activity (NEDA) status.

(Typical multiple sclerosis lesions were visible in a 2014 brain MRI)

CD4 count of the patient during the year

Between 2003 and 2005, the patient received a diagnosis of relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis (RRMS) and experienced four relapses. In 2006, the patient was diagnosed with HIV. It is important to note that no relapses or new lesions were observed between 2006 and 2007 when the patient's CD4 count ranged from 600 to 400 cells/mm³ prior to initiating highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART). The reliability of the results from 2007 and 2008 is questionable because the remission of MS could potentially be attributed to the low count of CD4 cells, ranging from 400 to 200. The normal range for CD4 count is typically between 500 and 1500 cells/mm³ (Battistini & Guzman, 2023).

Methods:

The patient's medical history, clinical symptoms, diagnostic radiology images, and treatment interventions were thoroughly examined. Furthermore, a review of relevant studies pertaining to the correlation between HIV infection and MS was conducted in order to Support the proposed hypothesis. Further research is needed.

Results:

The case study revealed a significant clinical improvement in MS symptoms following the diagnosis and treatment of HIV infection. This unexpected observation prompts an investigation into the potential genetic alterations induced by HIV integration and their impact on immune responses that is targeting the self-antigens.

Thesis:

(Environmental and biological factors can potentially lead to T-cell genes modifications that are involved in the recognition of self-antigens and cytokine production. These alterations may contribute to the regulation of autoimmune response targeting myelin sheaths)

Discussion:

Based on the case study evidence HIV integration modified important genes that may be reason that induced the autoimmune response. which explains why the patient experienced relief from multiple sclerosis symptoms after the HIV infection.

Treatment effect

Bone marrow transplant has emerged as a promising therapeutic option for highly active relapsing-remitting MS patients who don't respond to medications (Rush et al., 2018). Hematopoietic stem cell transplantation has demonstrated impressive results, with 67% of patients achieving no evidence of disease activity (NEDA) five years after the procedure (Sormani et al., 2016). This surpasses the rates observed in other clinical studies evaluating disease-modifying treatments.

Interestingly, a Swedish group consisting of highly active patients with relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis reported even more remarkable outcomes. They achieved NEDA percentages of 78% after two years and 68% after five years following transplantation. In comparison, the Halt MS trial recorded a NEDA or EFS (evidence of survive from disease) percentage of 69.2% over five years (Sormani et al., 2016). These findings shed light on the significant contribution of malfunctioning CD4 T cells to the development of MS, suggesting that factors related to T cell maturation or central/peripheral tolerance may not be the primary issue rather the issue may be in the genetic material of these T cells.

Despite the overall success of hematopoietic stem cell transplantation, it is crucial to acknowledge that around 10% of patients experienced a progression of multiple sclerosis after two years (Raffel et al., 2016). This phenomenon can potentially be attributed to T cells that evade the treatment process, migrate to the thymus for further development, and subsequently undergo clonal expansion. These modified cells play a crucial role in promoting MS development and facilitating survival.

MS and HIV cases

It is noteworthy that the occurrence rates of multiple sclerosis in patients with HIV were lower compared to those without HIV. The incidence ratio was found to be 0.53, indicating a reduced risk (McKay et al., 2023). When examining this relationship by gender, women living with HIV had even lower MS incidence rates, while men living with HIV had slightly higher but still relatively low MS incidence rates (Meglio, 2023b). This suggests that although it is possible to get infected with HIV and still develop MS, the occurrence is relatively rare, likely due to the variety of virus integration sites.

Vitamin D

The role of Vitamin D becomes significant in this context as it actively impacts the epigenome and regulate gene expression in various human tissues and cells. Sintzel et al. (2017) have provided an evidence of a significant correlation between

changed levels of vitamin D and the incidence of multiple sclerosis. Individuals with extreme higher and lower vitamin D levels have an elevated susceptibility to develop MS. Moreover, the Carlberg (2019) study shows that vitamin D have a direct effect on epigenome and expression of genes. This finding suggests that the inhibition or modification of specific genes may trigger an immune response against self-antigen

Genetics

Retroviruses like HIV and other viruses like EBV have been found to influence gene expression through their integration into DNA (Hughes & Coffin, 2016). Which explains why EBV has a great correlation with MS development as Bjernevik et al. (2022) study showed that the Risk of MS increased 32-fold after infection with EBV but wasn't increased after other viruses infection. The integration of these retroviruses may result in gene deletion, inhibition, or replacement which could lead to T cells recognizing self-components as foreign.

According to Schröder et al. (2002), HIV DNA preferentially integrates into areas of the genome that are rich in genes and have a high number of expressed genes. Furthermore, EBV, responsible for many health issues, has the ability to integrate its DNA into the host, particularly near promoter regions. This integration near important tumor suppressor genes like KANK1 has been observed in patients with T cell lymphoma (Xu et al., 2019). highlighting the potential role of gene repression in cancer development. In addition, when EBV integrates its DNA, it can alter important inflammation-related genes such as CDK15, TNFAIP3, and PARK2. These alterations may contribute to the development of multiple sclerosis, as well as nasopharyngeal cancer (Xu et al., 2019).

DMRT3 is a transcription factor involved in organizing spinal circuits that regulate walking patterns in vertebrates, plays a critical role in determining the types of neurons present in specific regions of the spinal cord and aiding in the formation of a synchronized network for controlling limb movements during locomotion (Perry et al., 2018). The loss and deletion of the DMRT3 gene during the integration of retrovirus DNA into the host genome may explain why T cells recognize nerve ganglia as foreign bodies

Mapping of EBV integration breakpoints

Notice genes in NK/T lymphoma (B)

Despite the fact that the patient's MS symptoms improved following their HIV diagnosis, other possible explanation for this could be the influence of HAART therapy on genes expression or direct effect on the virus.

Summary

By exploring the connections between HIV integration, genetic modifications, immune responses, and the impact of viruses like EBV, we gain a deeper understanding of the complex interplay of factors that influence the development and progression of multiple sclerosis. These findings highlight the intricate relationship between genetics, immune system dysfunction, and environmental factors, paving the way for potential future interventions and treatment

Future Work Suggestions

Further research is needed to identify the specific host genes affected by HIV integration and to understand the mechanisms underlying the observed remission of MS symptoms. Understanding the interplay between HIV infection and MS holds significant suggestions for developing therapeutic strategies aimed at modulating the immune response and improving outcomes in patients with MS.

REFERENCE:

1. Labella, F., Acebrón, F., Del Carmen Blanco-Valero, M., Rodríguez-Martín, A., Ortega, Á. M., & Morales, E. A. (2021). HIV infection and multiple sclerosis: a case with unexpected “no evidence of disease activity” status. *Journal of International Medical Research*, 49(3), 030006052199957. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0300060521999577>
2. Battistini Garcia, S. A., & Guzman, N. (2023). Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome CD4+ Count. In StatPearls. StatPearls Publishing.
3. Sormani, M. P., Muraro, P. A., Saccardi, R., & Mancardi, G. (2016). NEDA status in highly active MS can be more easily obtained with autologous hematopoietic stem cell transplantation than other drugs. *Multiple Sclerosis Journal*, 23(2), 201–204. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1352458516645670>
4. McKay, K. A., Wijnands, J. M. A., Manouchehrinia, A., Zhu, F., Sereda, P., Li, J., Ye, M., Trigg, J., Kooij, K., Ekström, A. M., Gisslén, M., Hillert, J., Hogg, R. S., Tremlett, H., & Kingwell, E. (2023). Risk of Multiple Sclerosis in People Living with HIV: An International Cohort Study. *Annals of Neurology*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ana.26840>
5. Meglio, M. (2023b, March 29). Understanding the risk of multiple sclerosis in patients with HIV. *Neurology Live*. <https://www.neurologylive.com/view/understanding-the-risk-of-multiple-sclerosis-patients-with-hiv>
6. Sintzel, M. B., Rametta, M., & Reder, A. T. (2017). Vitamin D and multiple sclerosis: A comprehensive review. *Neurology and Therapy*, 7(1), 59–85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40120-017-0086-4>
7. Rush, C. A., Atkins, H. L., & Freedman, M. S. (2018). Autologous hematopoietic stem cell transplantation in the treatment of multiple sclerosis. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Medicine*, 9(3), a029082. <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a029082>
8. Carlberg, C. (2019). Vitamin D: A micronutrient regulating genes. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*, 25(15), 1740–1746. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1381612825666190705193227>

9. Hughes, S. H., & Coffin, J. M. (2016). What Integration Sites Tell Us about HIV Persistence. *Cell Host & Microbe*, 19(5), 588–598.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chom.2016.04.010>
10. Schröder, A. R. W., Shinn, P., Chen, H., Berry, C., Ecker, J. R., & Bushman, F. (2002). HIV-1 integration in the human genome favors active genes and local hotspots. *Cell*, 110(4), 521–529.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0092-8674\(02\)00864-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0092-8674(02)00864-4)
11. Xu, M., Zhang, W., Zhu, Q., Yao, Y., Feng, Q., Zhang, Z., Peng, R., Jia, W., He, G., Feng, L., Zeng, Z., Luo, B., Xu, R., Zeng, M., Zhao, W., Chen, S., Zeng, Y., & Jiao, Y. (2019). Genome-wide profiling of Epstein-Barr virus integration by targeted sequencing in Epstein-Barr virus associated malignancies. *Theranostics*, 9(4), 1115–1124. <https://doi.org/10.7150/thno.29622>
12. Bjornevik, K., Cortese, M., Healy, B. C., Kuhle, J., Mina, M. J., Leng, Y., Elledge, S. J., Niebuhr, D. W., Scher, A. I., Munger, K. L., & Ascherio, A. (2022). Longitudinal analysis reveals high prevalence of Epstein-Barr virus associated with multiple sclerosis. *Science*, 375(6578), 296–301. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abj8222>
13. Perry, S., Larhammar, M., Vieillard, J., Nagaraja, C., Hilscher, M. M., Tafreshiha, A., Rofo, F., Caixeta, F. V., & Kullander, K. (2018). Characterization of Dmrt3-Derived Neurons Suggest a Role within Locomotor Circuits. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 39(10), 1771–1782. <https://doi.org/10.1523/jneurosci.0326-18.2018>